

IMPROVEMENT OF THE REGULATORY AND METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ENHANCING BUILDING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN AT THE PRESENT STAGE

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Abstract. *The article proposes an analytical approach to improving the regulatory and methodological system for enhancing building energy efficiency in Uzbekistan, taking into account the institutional and regulatory changes of 2024-2025. The evolution of the problem field in building thermal engineering, the transition from element-based requirements to integrated indicators of annual energy consumption, issues of acceptance and verification of actual energy performance, as well as the increasing role of renewable energy sources, digital monitoring, and environmental certification are considered. As a scientific result, an integrated model for modernizing the regulatory framework is proposed, combining requirements for building envelopes, engineering systems, energy certification, facility commissioning, digital metering, and economic evaluation of solutions based on the life-cycle cost criterion. It is shown that the current stage of regulatory development in Uzbekistan is characterized by a transition from fragmented standardization to a more comprehensive model including energy efficiency categories, revision of minimum standards, implementation of the “Green Building” certificate, mandatory consideration of alternative energy sources, and development of digital control mechanisms. Conclusions and recommendations aimed at preparing updated building codes and methodologies for the design, construction, and operation of energy-efficient buildings are formulated.*

Keywords: *energy efficiency, buildings, building thermal engineering, regulatory and technical framework, annual energy consumption, thermal protection, renewable energy sources, green construction, digital monitoring.*

1. Introduction

Enhancing building energy efficiency in Uzbekistan in recent years has acquired not only engineering but also pronounced institutional significance. The scale of residential construction remains high: within the framework of the housing provision program for 2025, the construction of 135 thousand apartments with a total area of 8.1 million m² is planned, which increases the requirements for the quality of design solutions, thermal protection, and resource efficiency of new facilities [8].

State policy is shifting from local energy-saving measures toward a systemic model in which energy efficiency is considered as part of the climate, investment, and urban development agenda. This is confirmed by the adoption of the Law “On Energy Saving, Rational Use of Energy and Increasing Energy Efficiency” (2024), the introduction of tasks for harmonizing building codes with international standards (2024), inclusion of the “Green Building” certificate in the state program for 2025, and adoption of special resolutions on reforming heat supply systems and improving building energy efficiency [1], [4]-[7].

The traditional approach limited to adjusting individual indicators of thermal resistance or engineering system capacity is no longer sufficient. Modern construction practice requires a coordinated system of requirements covering the building life cycle: from the selection of urban planning and structural solutions to commissioning, energy certification, digital metering, modernization, and operational control.

The purpose of the article is to develop an analytically substantiated project for improving the regulatory and methodological framework for enhancing building energy efficiency in Uzbekistan at the present stage. To achieve this goal, the following tasks are addressed: assessment of the current state of the regulatory environment; identification of persistent methodological limitations; analysis of the changes of 2024-2025; and formation of an integrated model for the further improvement of regulation in the construction sector.

2. Materials and Research Methods

The study was carried out on the basis of regulatory-legal and comparative-analytical approaches. The sources included the current legislative acts and urban planning standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the law on energy saving and increasing energy efficiency, documents on building thermal engineering, acts on harmonization of standards with international requirements, state programs for 2025, as well as resolutions regulating the use of solar panels, alternative heating systems, and digital monitoring mechanisms [1]-[9].

The methodological basis of the research includes: structural analysis of the regulatory system; comparative assessment by stages of the building life cycle; expert interpretation of the problems of transition from design capacity to actual annual energy consumption; as well as synthesis of the principles of cost-optimal and performance-based regulation used in international practice [10], [11].

The scientific novelty of the study is associated with integrating technical, institutional, and operational components of energy efficiency into a unified regulatory model, where the object of regulation is not only the structure or engineering system, but also the verifiable quality of building operation during the operational period.

Fig. 1. Evolution of the regulatory agenda for enhancing building energy efficiency in Uzbekistan in 2022-2025 (compiled by the author based on [1], [3]-[9])

3. Results and Discussion

1. Persistent Methodological Limitations of the Current System

Despite the significant development of construction regulation, a number of persistent limitations remain within the regulatory system. The first is associated with the predominance of element-based and calculated characteristics over integrated indicators of actual energy consumption. In practice, the quality of building envelopes and engineering systems is assessed mainly by individual parameters - thermal resistance, calculated heat losses, installed equipment capacity - whereas the actual operational efficiency of a building depends on total annual energy consumption, control regimes, user behavior, and the degree of system automation.

The second limitation concerns insufficient coordination between design standards, commissioning rules, and procedures for operational confirmation of energy performance. Even with a correct design, actual energy efficiency may decrease due to thermal inhomogeneities, installation defects, air permeability of joints, deviations in the adjustment of ventilation and heating systems, as well as the absence of verification of calculated indicators after commissioning.

The third limitation concerns the methodological basis for calculating reduced thermal resistance and accounting for thermal bridges. For modern façade and frame construction, this issue can no longer be ignored: as the thickness of thermal insulation increases, the contribution of linear and point thermal inhomogeneities to total losses also increases, which means that simple planar assessments cease to be sufficient.

The fourth group of problems relates to the economic aspect of standardization. Without a standardized methodology for assessing life-cycle cost, payback period, and operational effects, tightening requirements may prove either insufficient or excessive. Modernization of standards should rely not only on thermal engineering calculations, but also on verification of the technical and economic feasibility of solutions.

Table 1. Key Problems and Contemporary Directions for Their Regulatory Resolution

Problem block	Content of limitation	Current shifts in 2024-2025	Priority solution
Energy efficiency indicators	Predominance of element-based and capacity-based criteria over integrated assessment of operational energy consumption.	Law No. ZRU-940 introduces energy efficiency categories and minimum consumption standards with revision every 5 years [1].	Transition to standardization of specific annual energy consumption and EE classes.
Building thermal engineering	Insufficient consideration of thermal bridges, air permeability, and quality of envelope joints.	Amendments to KMK 2.01.04-2018 were introduced in 2024; harmonization with international standards has begun [3], [4].	Development of methodologies accounting for thermal bridges, air permeability, and envelope quality control

Operational verification	Gap between design calculations and actual building performance after commissioning.	The importance of energy passports, digital metering, and monitoring systems is increasing [1], [6], [7].	Mandatory verification of calculated and actual indicators at the commissioning stage.
Integration of renewable energy sources	RES are often considered as an external addition rather than part of the building regulatory model.	Requirements for solar panels in new residential buildings have been introduced; the use of alternative heating systems is expanding [7]-[9].	Establishment of RES requirements in design, commissioning, and operation.

2. Regulatory Shifts of 2024-2025 and Their Significance for the Construction Sector

A qualitative milestone was the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ZRU-940 of August 7, 2024 “On Energy Saving, Rational Use of Energy and Increasing Energy Efficiency.” For the construction sector, the law established a number of fundamentally important provisions: setting regulatory indicators for energy saving and increasing energy efficiency in building construction and residential premises; defining energy efficiency categories for buildings and structures with a usable area exceeding 200 m²; as well as revising minimum consumption standards for fuel and energy resources for buildings at least once every five years [1]. These provisions elevate energy saving from the status of a separate engineering task to the category of a mandatory element of construction regulation.

The second important direction was the modernization of building thermal engineering standards. In 2024, amendments and additions were introduced into KMK 2.01.04-2018 “Building Thermal Engineering,” and Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 231 dated April 23, 2024 established a course toward harmonization of construction regulations with international standards [3], [4]. Although the content of further updates requires phased detailing by individual sections, the institutional linkage of “adjustment of thermal engineering standards + international harmonization” itself signifies a transition to a new logic of rulemaking.

In 2025, the agenda was further strengthened by environmental and operational mechanisms. The State Program for implementing the “Uzbekistan - 2030” Strategy in the “Year of Environmental Protection and Green Economy” directly provides for the introduction of the “Green Building” certificate based on the energy efficiency of newly constructed buildings, structures, and residential houses [5]. This is particularly important for construction science, as it creates prerequisites for transitioning from minimum permissible standards to differentiated assessment of building quality.

Presidential Resolution No. PP-100 dated March 11, 2025 linked heat supply reform with the tasks of increasing building energy efficiency and reducing energy losses through the application of innovative technologies [6]. Presidential Resolution No. PP-133 dated April 1, 2025 provided for the widespread use of electrical and alternative energy sources, as well as energy-saving technologies in the design and construction of multi-storey residential and public buildings; furthermore, the document strengthened the role of digital monitoring and reporting platforms [7].

Additional significance for the housing sector is provided by the provisions of Presidential Decree No. UP-26 dated February 21, 2025 on the development of housing and mortgage markets. For new residential areas, principles of urbanization, availability of engineering infrastructure, and allocation of at least 2% of construction costs for creating green zones were established, while the widespread use of RES installations, energy-efficient equipment, heat pumps, and solar water heaters was recommended in the construction of new infrastructure [8]. Building energy efficiency is increasingly considered as part of spatial and infrastructure development.

In 2023, an important technological precedent was established: Presidential Resolution No. PP-57 introduced the requirement to install solar panels on at least 50% of the free roof area of new multi-storey residential buildings, while buildings without grid-connected solar panels are not accepted into operation [9]. This decision effectively linked building commissioning requirements with the presence of operational RES-based energy infrastructure.

Fig. 2. Integrated model of regulatory support for enhancing building energy efficiency (compiled by the author)

3. Proposed Model for Improving the Regulatory and Methodological Framework

Taking into account the identified limitations and recent legislative changes, the further development of the regulatory system may be structured through six interrelated contours.

The first contour is building envelopes. Here, a transition is required from simplified requirements to a more accurate assessment of reduced thermal resistance with mandatory consideration of linear, point, and volumetric thermal inhomogeneities. For this purpose, it is necessary to develop a national catalog of standard joints, heat loss coefficients, and air permeability classes of modern building envelopes, as well as to link calculation procedures with actual series of materials and products used in Uzbekistan.

The second contour is engineering systems and renewable energy sources. The practice of 2023-2025 demonstrates that RES are already becoming part of mandatory requirements for new buildings [7]-[9]. Consequently, building standards should move from the wording “application is permitted” to a model in which “the possibility and conditions of integration are normatively

established,” including requirements for solar installations, heat pumps, solar DHW systems, storage systems, and automation.

The third contour concerns annual energy consumption indicators. For residential and public buildings, it is necessary to establish standards for specific annual energy consumption at least for heating, ventilation, cooling, and hot water supply, and in the future for total final and primary energy consumption. Such an approach allows objective comparison of buildings, formation of energy efficiency classes, and evaluation of results not according to design declarations but according to verifiable operational performance.

The fourth contour is commissioning and verification. At the stage of commissioning a facility, it is advisable to establish mandatory building energy certification, testing of air permeability and engineering system adjustment, as well as comparison of calculated and actual parameters according to a standardized procedure. Phased verification schemes - basic, extended, and advanced - may be applied for different building types.

The fifth contour is digital monitoring and metering. Under modern conditions, energy efficiency without data becomes declarative. Therefore, metering devices, automated engineering equipment control systems, and information platforms should be considered part of the regulatory architecture. Strengthening of this direction is already reflected in the legal acts of 2025, which provide for the development of digital monitoring and reporting platforms [7].

The sixth contour is economic and environmental assessment. New requirements should be evaluated according to the cost-optimal criterion, i.e., based on the minimum discounted life-cycle costs of a building, taking into account capital investments, maintenance, energy expenses, RES effects, and equipment replacement costs [11]. The linkage of cost-optimal analysis with “Green Building” certification makes it possible to ensure that modernization of standards is simultaneously engineering-based and investment-realistic.

Table 2. Priority Directions for Modernizing the Building Energy Efficiency Improvement System

Life-cycle stage	Object of regulation	Required update	Expected effect
Design	Building envelopes and joints	Methodologies for calculating reduced thermal resistance considering thermal inhomogeneities, catalog of standard joints, air permeability requirements.	Reduction of the gap between calculated and operational performance.
Design	Engineering systems and RES	Establishment of integration conditions for solar systems, heat pumps, and automation.	Increase in the share of low-carbon solutions.
Expert review	Energy indicators	Verification of annual energy consumption and EE class within design documentation.	Increased objectivity of expert assessment.

Construction and commissioning	Actual characteristics	Energy passport, inspection of joints, system adjustment, confirmation of RES connection.	Reliability of facility commissioning.
Operation	Metering and monitoring	Integration of meters and digital platforms, periodic consumption reporting.	Transition to data-driven building management.
Modernization	Economic efficiency	Standardized feasibility study and cost-optimal methodology for renovation and refurbishment.	Rational selection of measures during modernization of the building stock.

4. Scientific and Practical Significance of the Proposed Approach

The proposed model is important for both rulemaking and applied construction science. First, it makes it possible to coordinate research in the fields of thermal protection, engineering systems, RES, and automation within a common methodological framework focused on verifiable building performance. Such an approach contributes to the formation of new topics for applied research: development of national catalogs of thermal inhomogeneities, adaptation of in situ verification methods, modeling of annual energy consumption for various climatic zones of Uzbekistan, and assessment of the impact of solar systems on the integrated energy balance of buildings.

For design and construction practice, the value of the approach lies in resolving the contradiction between the rigidity of standards and the flexibility of engineering solutions. The clearer the final regulatory indicator is formulated - annual energy consumption, EE class, verified system performance - the greater the scope for engineering optimization. In this context, building energy efficiency is directly associated with the quality of design solutions, digital measurability of results, and controllability of building operation.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

1. The current stage of development of the regulatory and methodological framework for building energy efficiency in Uzbekistan is characterized by a transition from predominantly element-based regulation to a more complex multi-component model including regulatory indicators, energy efficiency categories, environmental certification, digital monitoring, and integration of RES [1], [5]-[9].

2. A key achievement of recent years has been the institutional consolidation of energy efficiency as an independent subject of regulation in the construction sector, including the definition of energy efficiency categories for buildings with an area exceeding 200 m² and the mandatory periodic revision of minimum energy consumption standards [1].

3. At the same time, methodological gaps remain related to the consideration of thermal bridges, the absence of a unified procedure for verification of actual building characteristics, and insufficient regulatory orientation toward annual energy consumption rather than only the design capacities of engineering systems.

4. A justified direction for further development is the creation of an integrated regulatory system according to the stages of the building life cycle: design - expert review - construction - commissioning - operation - modernization.

5. For updating building standards, it is advisable to:

- a) establish indicators of specific annual energy consumption and EE classes;
- b) develop a national catalog of thermal inhomogeneities and methodologies for accurate calculation of reduced thermal resistance;
- c) make the energy passport and operational verification part of the commissioning procedure;
- d) link standards with digital metering and automation;
- e) use the cost-optimal approach and the “Green Building” certificate as tools for selecting and evaluating solutions.

6. The proposed approach may serve as a basis for developing updated scientific and practical recommendations for improving building standards, residential building stock renovation programs, as well as educational and methodological materials for training specialists in the field of energy-efficient construction.

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